

SOME SIX-CO-ORDINATED COMPLEXES OF NICKEL(II):
NITRITO-AMMINES OF NICKEL(II)

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Several nitrito-ammines of nickel(II) have been prepared, viz., $\text{Ni}[\text{o-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2]_2(\text{NO}_2)_2$, $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2$ and $\text{Ni}_3[\text{H}_2\text{NCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2]_2(\text{NO}_2)_3(\text{OH})$. These are all red in colour, insoluble in water and paramagnetic with a moment of about 3 Bohr magnetons. These are believed to be six-co-ordinated nickel(II) complexes, and a polynuclear structure has therefore been assigned to the ethylenediamine complex.

Nitrito-ammines of nickel(II) of the type $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{B}_4$, where $\text{B}=\text{NH}_3$ or $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}$, are already known (Erdmann, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1866, i, 97, 385; Abegg, 'Handbuch der anorganischen Chemie', Vol. 4, Part iv, No. 1, pp. 690, 731, Verlag von S. Hirzel in Leipzig, 1937). Although the crystals of the pyridine compound are bluish green in colour, the ammonia compound forms beautiful cherry-red crystals. The colour is peculiar to this salt and this was remarked upon by Ephraim (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 3101) who assigned to it the constitution $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2$. The magnetic moment of this complex compound was measured by Nyholm (cf. Palmer, "Experimental Inorganic Chemistry", p. 561, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1954) who found this to be paramagnetic with $\mu=3.09$ Bohr magnetons. Since, it is rather well known (Pauling, "The Nature of the Chemical Bond", pp. 119, 122, 123, Cornell University Press, Ithaca, 1948; Rây, "The Theory of Valency and the Structure of Chemical Compounds", p. 52, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta, 1946) that in the four-covalent complexes of nickel(II) those with red, reddish brown or yellow colour are diamagnetic, while those with blue, bluish green or green colour are paramagnetic, it may safely be assumed that $\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2$ contains six-covalent nickel(II), as was suggested earlier by Ephraim (*loc. cit.*). This possibly contains d^2sp^3 or sp^3d^2 bonds, presumably the latter type where the two unpaired electrons have not been raised to an outer level. In either case, there should be two unpaired electrons to account for the observed moment of 3.09 Bohr magnetons.

This paper contains a report on the preparations and properties of several other six-co-ordinated nickel(II) complexes which have been carried out in this laboratory. Of the various amines that have been studied, only *o*-phenylenediamine, benzylamine and ethylenediamine have been found to give rise to red coloured insoluble complexes by interaction with nickel salts in presence of an excess of sodium nitrite in aqueous solution. However, methylamine, ethylamine, diethylamine, ethanolamine and cyclohexylamine failed to produce any such nickel complex, but instead formed a precipitate of green nickel hydroxide on adding to a solution of a nickel salt (sulphate, chloride or acetate) containing a large excess of sodium nitrite. The *o*-phenylenediamine and benzylamine complexes have the composition $\text{Ni}[\text{o-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2]_2(\text{NO}_2)_2$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2$, respectively. The ethylenediamine compound, however, is somewhat

different and unlike the previous two compounds it separates gradually from a solution of the constituents on long standing. Analysis of nickel, total nitrogen and nitrite indicates a composition $\text{Ni}_2[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2]_2(\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{OH})$. All the three compounds are red in colour, insoluble in water, and are paramagnetic with a moment of about 3 Bohr magnetons. These therefore possibly contain six-co-ordinated nickel(II). The following polynuclear structure might be suggested for the ethylenediamine complex :

The other two compounds have a simple structure analogous to that of the ammonia compound, already referred to.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dinitro-bis-o-phenylenediamine-nickel(II).—A solution of nickel acetate (6 g.) in water (30 c.c.) was mixed with *o*-phenylenediamine (5.5 g.) in alcohol (40 c.c.). This was cooled in an ice-bath and to it was gradually added with stirring a solution of 25 g. of sodium nitrite in 30 c.c. of water. Stirring was continued for 15 minutes in the cold and thereafter the red coloured precipitate of the nickel complex was filtered off in a Büchner funnel under suction, washed thoroughly with ice-cold water and finally with alcohol, and then dried in vacuo over fused calcium chloride. {Found : Ni, 16.00 ; N, 23.63. $\text{Ni}_1[\text{o-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2]_2(\text{NO}_2)_2$ requires Ni, 16.01 ; N, 22.91%}.

The substance is a red powder, insoluble in ethyl alcohol, ether, acetone and chloroform. It is insoluble in cold water but is decomposed by hot water as well as by alkalis, forming green nickel hydroxide. It is also decomposed by acids, aqueous ammonia and ethylenediamine, forming clear solutions. The compound is paramagnetic : $\chi_g = 1028 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m(\text{cor.}) = 3873 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_s = 3.09$.

Dinitrito-tetrakis-benzylamine-nickel(II).—A solution of nickel acetate (5 g.) and sodium nitrite (20 g.) in water (150 c.c.) was warmed on the water-bath and to it was added slowly with stirring benzylamine (9 c.c.). After the addition of the last drop the mixture, containing the red precipitate of the nickel complex, was kept on the water-bath for 15 minutes more and then filtered under suction as usual. The red solid was washed with an ice-cold solution of very dilute ammonia (approx. 0.3N) and then dried in vacuo over fused calcium chloride. (Found : Ni, 10.36 ; N, 14.89. $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2$ requires Ni, 10.14 ; N, 14.52%).

The substance is a red powder, insoluble in ethyl alcohol or ether in the cold but is decomposed on warming with the solvent. It is also decomposed slowly by acetone, chloroform, etc., forming a greenish turbidity, and more readily by water even in the cold,

forming nickel hydroxide, although stable to even hot water containing benzylamine and excess of sodium nitrite. It is decomposed as usual by acids, alkalies, aqueous ammonia, ethylenediamine, etc. It is paramagnetic : $\chi_g = 5.48 \times 10^{-6}$; χ_m (cor.) = 3361×10^{-6} ; $\mu_s = 2.88$.

$Ni_2(en)_2(NO_2)_2(OH)$.—A solution of nickel acetate (5 g) and sodium nitrite (20 g.) in water (50 c.c.) was cooled in an ice-bath and a concentrated aqueous solution of ethylenediamine was added dropwise with stirring till the dark green solution turned violet in colour. The stirring was continued for 1 hour and the clear solution was kept in a covered beaker for several days at room temperature (about 25°) when red crystals separated gradually from the solution. This was filtered off, washed first with ice-cold water, then with alcohol and dried over fused calcium chloride in vacuo. (Found : Ni, 30.24 ; N, 24.92 ; NO_2^- , 35.80. $Ni_2[C_2H_4(NH_2)_2]_2(NO_2)_2(OH)$ requires Ni, 30.02 ; N, 24.94 ; NO_2^- , 35.14%).

The substance is red in colour and is insoluble in ethyl alcohol, ether, acetone and chloroform. It is highly insoluble in cold water but is decomposed by hot water and alkalies, forming some nickel hydroxide and a bluish violet solution, presumably containing $[Ni(en)_2]^{2+}$ ion. It is also decomposed as usual by acids, aqueous ammonia and ethylenediamine. It is paramagnetic : $\chi_g = 19.6 \times 10^{-6}$; χ_m (cor.) = 3924×10^{-6} ; $\mu_s = 3.11$.

Analytical Procedures.—Nickel was estimated gravimetrically as nickel dimethylglyoxime after decomposing the substance with hot sulphuric acid. Nitrogen (total) was estimated by semi-micro combustion, while the nitrite in the ethylenediamine complex was estimated by decomposing the complex by digestion with 0.1N-KOH and diluting the filtered solution containing the nitrite to a definite volume and estimating the nitrite in the solution by permanganate method as usual. Ethylenediamine present in the nitrite solution did not interfere with the titration. However, in the case *o*-phenylenediamine or benzylamine complex, this method did not work. Attempts to separate the amines by solvent-extraction were also unsuccessful and hence, nitrite content of these complexes could not be estimated directly.

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